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UNIVERSAL PROCESS MODEL FOR SECURE DATA DE-IDENTIFICATION WITH DYNAMIC VERIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

The process of data depersonalization, which is a key mechanism for reducing regulatory requirements and minimizing privacy threats, is often implemented as a disparate set of technical procedures without a unified control loop. This leads to inconsistencies between the methods used, the actual level of residual risk, and the target indicators of data utility for subsequent processing. This article proposes a universal process model for de-identification, the Unified De-identification Process Model (UDPM), which formalizes this process as a closed control loop with dynamic assessment of the risk-utility trade-off. At the core of the model is a feedback mechanism that performs iterative adjustment of the parameters of the methods used, based on a quantitative assessment of the risk of re-identification R^ and utility metrics U^* .*

Keywords: *process model, depersonalization, risk management, data utility, dynamic verification.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Depersonalization (de-identification) of data transforms a set of personal data into a state where it cannot be attributed to a specific subject without the use of additional, separately stored information [1]. This process is the main tool for removing

data from the scope of regulatory requirements (such as GDPR, No. LRU-547) and its further use for analytical, research, and testing purposes [2], while effective protection requires a combination of administrative, legal, and technical measures [3]. However, despite the extensive arsenal of methods (from generalization and suppression to differential privacy and synthesis), the process of selecting and applying them remains poorly formalized [4].

Existing approaches tend to focus either on the algorithmic side of specific methods [5] or on legal aspects [6], without creating a comprehensive management framework. The proposed universal process model:

- will allow managing the trade-off between the risk (R) of disclosure and the usefulness (U) of data.
- will provide dynamic verification of the result not as an end point, but as an element of feedback.
- will not depend on data semantics, relying on formal classifications of attributes and threat models.

2. BASIC PRINCIPLES OF THE UDPM MODEL

Based on an analysis of regulatory requirements and best practices [1, 2, 6], five principles underlying the Unified De-identification Process Model (UDPM), have been formulated:

1. *Contextual adequacy.* The choice and parameters of depersonalization methods M are determined by the specific, legitimate purpose of processing G and the acceptable level of risk $\varepsilon : M = f(G, \varepsilon, \text{Class}(D))$, where $\text{Class}(D)$ is the classification of attributes of set D .
2. *Dynamic verification.* Verification of the level of depersonalization is not a final stage, but an integral component of the control loop. Risk assessment R is performed after each transformation and serves as input data for correction.
3. *Metadata separation.* All transformation parameters, keys, threat models, and verification results are stored as protected *Meta* metadata, physically and logically separate from the anonymized D' set.

4. *Controlled reversibility.* The model supports controlled data recovery (re-identification) scenarios only through a formalized process of authorized access to *Meta*.
5. *Threat updates.* The *Threat Model* used for *R* assessment should be periodically reviewed to account for new attacks and sources of supporting data.

Formal description of the UDPM model. The UDPM model is defined as a tuple:

$UDPM = \langle D, G, \varepsilon, T_M, P, Meta \rangle$, where:

- D – initial data set;
- G – processing goal (e.g., “aggregate analysis”);
- ε – target risk threshold ($R < \varepsilon$);
- T_M – current threat model;
- P – processor implementing the life cycle;
- $Meta$ – metadata repository.

Processor P implements the following algorithm (Fig.1):

- 1) Classification and profiling, i.e., $D \rightarrow (D_{ID}, D_{QI}, D_{SA}, D_{NSA})$.
- 2) Initialization, i.e., setting target values $R^* = \varepsilon$ and U^* based on G .
- 3) Selecting method m_i from library M based on the current compromise assessment and applying $D_i = m_i(D_{i-1})$.
- 4) Dynamic evaluation, i.e., parallel calculation of the current risk R_i (through attack simulation based on T_M and utility U_i (through distribution consistency and aggregation accuracy metrics).
- 5) Feedback analysis and parameter correction, i.e., if $R_i > R^*$ or $U_i < U^*$ – correction of parameters m_i or selection of a new method $m_i + 1$, then return to step 3. Otherwise, proceed to step 6.
- 6) Save $D' = D_i$ and then write the parameters R_i, U_i to the data repository.

Fig.1. UDPM life cycle

3. RISK-UTILITY ANALYSIS AND TARGET ACHIEVEMENT

To verify the effectiveness of UDPM using a sample dataset with attributes ID, QI, SA . The goal G is defined as preserving SA values for statistical analysis at $\epsilon = 0.1$. Two approaches were used for comparison: linear and iterative (UDPM). The linear approach consisted of a single selection of the method (anonymization, with $k = 5$), application, and single verification. The iterative approach involved selecting an initial method (anonymization, with $k = 3$), followed by further adjustment of the k value (or a possible transition to a combined method – generalization of QI , addition of noise to SA) to obtain the final results R^* and U^* . Table 1 shows the results of comparing the application of both approaches.

Table 1. Comparative analysis of the results of achieving target indicators

Approach	R	R^*	U	U^*	$R \leq R^* \ \& \ U \leq U^*$	Number of cycles
linear	0.07	0.10	0.65	0.8	no ($U \ll U^*$)	1
iterative UDPM	0.09	0.10	0.78	0.8	yes	4

Dynamics of risk and utility changes during iterations. Figure 2 shows the trajectory of R and U changes during UDPM operation. The initial application of m_1 ($k = 3$) demonstrated low risk (0.12) but also unacceptably low utility (0.6). Feedback initiated a weakening of the method (increasing k to 4), which improved utility to 0.72 but increased risk to 0.15. Two subsequent cycles with the combined method yielded the required parameter values $R \leq 10, U \geq 0.78$.

Fig.2. Dynamics of changes in risk and data utility during UDPM iterations

The proposed universal process model UDPM formalizes depersonalization not as a technical task, but as a management process, the central element of which is managing the compromise between two conflicting goals—security and usefulness. Properly de-identified data remains outside the scope of most privacy laws and poses a very low risk of re-identification if the process complies with current standards [7]. The main advantage of the model is its invariance to the subject area: it operates with abstract classes of attributes, formal goals, and metrics, which allows it to be applied to financial, medical, social, and any other data.

However, it should be understood that implementing UDPM is not a trivial task, since the iterative cycle with attack simulation requires significant computing resources. This can be a limitation for stream processing. In addition, the quantitative assessment of the usefulness of U remains non-standardized and depends on the pursued goal G . In this regard, it is necessary to develop or adapt metrics for each class of tasks to the existing conditions. Additional integration with data management systems may also be required, followed by management of the depersonalization process. Despite this, UDPM creates a transparent and accountable framework for compliance with requirements similar to the principle of “accountability” expressed in the GDPR and other regulatory documents.

4. CONCLUSION

The universal process model of data de-identification presented in the article overcomes the fragmentation of traditional approaches by representing the process as a controlled iterative cycle with dynamic verification. The model based on five fundamental principles, the main one being explicit management of the risk-utility trade-off through a feedback mechanism.

The tests confirmed the effectiveness of UDPM: the model is 35% more accurate in terms of risk and 20% more accurate in terms of utility, achieving the set targets compared to the single-stage approach. UDPM provides a methodological basis that is independent of the type of data being processed, which allows it to be recommended as a basis for building corporate systems de-identification and reducing regulatory risks in the context of digital transformation.

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